

A GREEK FROM KITION NAMED PEISON OR PEITHON AS PUPIL OF PANAETIUS – AND
NO ROMAN ARISTOCRAT PISO (PHLD. IND. STOIC. COL. 74)

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Abstract The article confirms recent doubts about the identification of a Peison (Piso) mentioned in a list of pupils of the Stoic Panaetius with the Roman historian and politician Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi or another Roman Piso (Phld. Ind. Stoic. col. 74). A new reading (based on the virtual replacement of a sottoposto) shows that the person mentioned in the papyrus came from Kition. His name was either Peison or Peithon and he was obviously a Greek, not a Roman.

keywords Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi, Panaetius, Philodemus, Index Stoicorum, Kition

Recently, Cardinali has argued that a certain Πείσων, whose name occurs in a list of pupils of the Stoic philosopher Panaetius (c. 185–110 BCE) preserved in Philodemus' *Index Stoicorum*, should not be identified with the Roman aristocrat and historian Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi (consul in 133 BCE).¹ Consequently, he concludes, the occurrence of the name Πείσων in the list can no longer be regarded as evidence of alleged Stoic elements in the *Annales* of Piso Frugi or of a Stoic influence on this character. Column 74 of the *Index Stoicorum* in the last edition by Dorandi reads as follows:²

Phld. Ind. Stoic. (P.Herc. 1018) col. 74

Μάρκιος καὶ Νύσιος

Σαυνῖται· Νύσιος δὲ καὶ

τὸ τῶν σπουδαιοπα-

ρώ<ι>δων γένος πρῶτος

5 ἐ[π]ενόησεν· Παράμο-

νος Ταρσ]εύς· Πεί[σ]ων

...]ευσ[.]τι[

¹ This project has received funding from the ERC Advanced Grant 885222 “GreekSchools” and the DFG-project “Die Geschichte der Stoa aus Herkulaneum”. I would like to thank Graziano Ranocchia for his comments. L. Cardinali, “Uno storico stoiceggiante nella Roma del II sec a. C.?,” *Giornale Italiano di Filologia* 73 (2021) 115–126. On Panaetius, see F. Alesse, *Panezio di Rodi e la tradizione stoica* (Naples 1994); J. Gourinat and F. Alesse, “Panétius de Rhodes,” in R. Goulet (ed.), *Dictionnaire des philosophes antiques* 5 (Paris 2012) 131–138. Fragments collected by F. Alesse, *Panezio di Rodi. Testimonianze* (Naples 1997). On Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi and the remains of his work see for instance H. Beck/U. Walter, *Die frühen römischen Historiker* (vol. 1) (Darmstadt 2001) 282–329.

² T. Dorandi, *Filodemo, Storia dei filosofi: La stoa da Zenone a Panezio (PHerc. 1018)* (Leiden 1994). Previous editions: D. Comparetti, “Papiro ercolanese inedito,” *Rivista di Filologia e Istruzione Classica* 3 (1875) 449–555; A. Traversa, *Index Herculanensis* (Genoa 1952). The *Index Stoicorum* represents a book (volume) of Philodemus' *Σύνταξις τῶν φιλοσόφων*, which consisted of at least ten books (D.L. 10,3). In addition to the *Index Stoicorum*, substantial portions of the *Index Academicorum* and sparse fragments from other books can be found in the Herculaneum papyri. On the structure and content of the *syntaxis* see K. Fleischer, *Philodem. Geschichte der Akademie. Einführung, Ausgabe, Kommentar* (Leiden 2023) 11–25; and, on the structure and content the *Index Stoicorum*, see G. Ranocchia, “La Vita di Aristone di Chio nella Rassegna degli Stoici di Filodemo (P.Herc. 1018, coll. 10 e 33–37). Edizione, introduzione e commento,” *Analecta Papirologica* 22 (2020) 8–156.

The first editor of the *Index Stoicorum* Comparetti tentatively proposed the identification of the Piso in the list with Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi.³ Several scholars agreed with his suggestion,⁴ while many others did not completely reject the identification, but pointed out that not only Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi, but also many other Roman “Pisones” of that period could have been pupils of Panaetius, so that the identity of the Piso in the list must remain uncertain. The various arguments put forward by Cardinali against the identification with the politician and historian Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi are rather compelling. He reasonably supposes that an *ethnicon* ending in εὺς was written in line 7, referring to a Greek city where a native Greek with the name Πείσω or Πείθων (and not a Roman with the cognomen Piso) lived. He concludes, that, in any case, the *Index Stoicorum* cannot be taken as evidence that Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi was ever a pupil of Panaetius and/or that this discipleship had any influence on his personality or works.⁵ I may add that the possible mention of a Roman Piso would also justify some speculation as to whether Philodemus (110–40/30 BCE) added this very Piso to the list of his original source, since he enjoyed the patronage of Lucius Calpurnius Piso Caesoninus (Cesar’s father-in-law and consul in 58 BCE) and wanted to include an ancestor of the family (in the broadest sense) in his *Index Stoicorum*.⁶

I am currently preparing a new comprehensive edition of Philodemus’ *Index Stoicorum* (P.Herc. 1018), which includes an exhaustive bibliometric and stratigraphic survey of the entire papyrus scroll. In the context of the Herculaneum papyri, stratigraphy concerns the presence of different layers, that were misplaced during the mechanical unrolling of the papyrus scroll in modern times.⁷ In the right margin of column 74 some minor *sottoposti* can be detected in different lines, some of which are more or less physically connected (fig. 1). Although it is difficult to visually identify these *sottoposti* in column 74, i.e. to distinguish between the ground layer and the layer below, their slight displacement with respect to the ground level and lexical reasons reveal or confirm the existence of different layers. For instance, at the end of line four, the right part of an ω and the left part of a δ are placed somewhat below the level of the main (base) line (which is partly lost at the end of the column). For lexical reasons, the virtual replacement of these two letters towards the beginning of line 4 is beyond doubt (the right part of the δ, matching the displaced left part of it, is still preserved at the beginning of line 4). In this section of the papyrus, all *sottoposti* must be shifted exactly 4 cm to the left (the width of the circumference of the scroll at this winding). Moreover, they must be moved slightly upwards, since there is a slight vertical displacement due to the unrolling or the gluing on the cornice, as indicated by the virtual replacement in line 4.

³ Comparetti (n. 2) 544–545 (“Il Pisone qui nominato non può essere altri che L. Calpurnio Pisone Frugiqui senza dubbio figura come uditore di questo filosofo, cosa che altri autori non ci tramandarono, ma che si accorda perfettamente con quanto sappiamo sul carattere e la vita di quel personaggio.”). It may be worth mentioning Cardinali’s remark (Cardinali (n. 1) 123 n. 42) that Comparetti’s suggestion ὑπατ]εύς[ας (Comparetti (n. 2) 544) is unlikely in this position (i.e. immediately after the name).

⁴ Cardinali (n. 1) 116 gives a list of many of these scholars. For skepticism about the possibility of exact identification of the Piso in the *Index Stoicorum* see for instance M. Schanz and C. Hosius, *Geschichte der römischen Literatur (II)* (Munich 1926)⁴ 195 and N. Berti, “La decadenza morale di Roma ed i “viri antiqui”. Riflessioni su alcuni frammenti degli Annali di L. Calpurnio Pisone Frugi,” *Prometheus* 15 (1989) 54. For the many Pisones in the 2nd century BCE, see D. Earl, “Calpurnii Pisones in the second century BC,” *Athenaeum* 38 (1960) 283–298.

⁵ Cardinali (n. 1) 122–124.

⁶ For Philodemus’ biography and dates see for instance Fleischer (n. 2) 26–32. Philodemus addresses Piso in one epigram (*AP* 11,44 = Epigram 27 Sider) and dedicates the *De bono rege secundum Homerum* (P.Herc. 1507) to him. In particular, we know about their relationship through Cicero’s lively description in his speech *In Pisonem* (68–72). One could go even further and imagine that the aforementioned Samnites, who lived near (or even in) the Bay of Naples, where Philodemus and Piso stayed, somehow triggered the mention of a Roman Piso in the following lines.

⁷ F. Nicolardi, “Aspetti e problemi della stratigrafia nei papiri ercolanesi: lo spostamento a catena di sovrapposti e sottoposti,” *CErc* 49 (2019) 191–216.

An autopsy of the original papyrus in Naples enabled me to identify another *sottoposto* at the end of line 7, which earlier editors and the *disegnatore* had mistaken for a genuine part of line 7 (the ground layer).⁸ The *sottoposto* contains the letters τ and the left part of a curve. As explained above, this *sottoposto* must be shifted exactly 4 cm to the left and slightly upwards (fig. 2). The rightmost part of the *sottoposto* with part of a curve matches exactly the missing part of the curve of the (partly) preserved ϵ of the sequence $\epsilon\upsilon\varsigma$ in the ground layer.⁹ Accordingly, the transposition of the *sottoposto* gives us the sequence $\tau\epsilon\upsilon\varsigma$, which was written in the original papyrus. At the beginning of line 7 there is space for little more than a normal letter before $\tau\epsilon\upsilon\varsigma$, not for three letters as in Dorandi's edition. The only possible supplement is $\text{Κ}\tau\epsilon\upsilon\varsigma$. The Stoic philosopher and pupil of Panaetius mentioned in col. 74 hailed from Kition, the same famous *polis* from which Zeno, the founder of the Stoa, also came.

Finally, the *Neapolitan Disegno* (fig. 3) suggests π before $\epsilon\iota$, even if nowadays only a small part of the right horizontal survives.¹⁰ The space after $\epsilon\iota$ allows for a rather narrow letter. The autopsy (see figure 1) confirms Cardinali's remark that $\text{Π}\epsilon\iota[\sigma]\omega\nu$ is not really more likely than $\text{Π}\epsilon\iota[\theta]\omega\nu$, both well attested Greek names in the Classical, Hellenistic and Imperial period.¹¹ Given the obvious focus on Greek pupils in the list, which can also be observed in the *Index Academicorum* for the pupils of the Academics Philio of Larissa, Antiochus of Ascalon and Charmadas of Alexandria,¹² and given the origin from Kition, the philosopher in question is more likely to have heard Panaetius in Athens than in Rome.

To sum up: The correct virtual replacement of a *sottoposto* excludes once and for all that Lucius Calpurnius Piso Frugi (or any other Roman with the cognomen Piso) is mentioned as a pupil of the Stoic Panaetius in col. 74,6–7 of the *Index Stoicorum*. Instead, the individual listed as a pupil of Panaetius is an otherwise unknown (native) Greek from Kition with the Greek name of $\text{Π}\epsilon\iota\sigma\omega\nu$ or $\text{Π}\epsilon\iota\theta\omega\nu$.

fig. 1: Phld. *Ind. Stoic.* col. 74

(Near-Infrared image at 1000 nm – ERC Advanced Grant 885222 *GreekSchools*. By courtesy of Italy's Ministry of Culture (CNR-Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale/Biblioteca Nazionale 'Vittorio Emanuele III', Napoli)

⁸ Comparetti (n. 2) had already recognized that the “alignment” was out of place, but had not concluded that the letters represented a *sottoposto* (“In R (= Neapolitan Disegno) non è segnato che TI in fine. Queste due lettere sono alquanto inferiori al livello della linea, forse per effetto di spostamento del papiro in quel luogo.”).

⁹ What we often find is that the *disegnatori* of the *Neapolitan Disegni* “mentally” supplemented missing smaller parts of letters. In this case the small missing lower part of the ϵ was drawn in the disegno, but is actually found on the *sottoposto*.

¹⁰ The *disegno* was drawn by Luigi Corazza in 1808, when the papyrus was in a better state of preservation than it is today. For a closer analysis of the *disegni* of P.Herc. 1018, see Ranocchia (n. 3) 55–56.

¹¹ See Cardinali (n. 1) 123 n. 43 and the *LGPN*, which has no entries for a Peison or Peithon from Kition.

¹² Cf. Phld. *Ind. Acad.* col. 34,6–19; 35,2–36,8. For the name Philio (with a second Iota) see K. Fleischer, “Philo or Philio of Larissa?,” *CQ* 72 (2022) 222–232.

fig. 2: Phld. *Ind. Stoic.* col. 74 with virtually replaced sottoposto

(Near-Infrared image at 1000 nm- ERC Advanced Grant 885222 GreekSchools. By courtesy of Italy's Ministry of Culture (CNR-Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale/Biblioteca Nazionale 'Vittorio Emanuele III', Napoli)

fig. 3 Phld. *Ind. Stoic.* col. 74 – Neapolitan Disegno

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